

Exchange Rate Exposure for Aircraft Operating Leases - An Airline Operations Perspective

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Abstract

Aircraft leasing is a process through which airlines bring in the aircraft from other leasing companies or airlines as part of their capacity addition. Globally, over 50% of the commercial aircraft fleet is on a lease basis. In India, over 70% of the airline fleet is on an operating lease basis, and the same trend is expected to be continued. In return for the leased asset, airlines pay huge fixed monthly rentals to the leasing companies and usually in USD. As regards, the airlines are exposing to foreign exchange fluctuation. The depreciation of the local currency as against the USD will bring additional financial burden and revenue leakage into Indian carriers and thus affecting the sustainable operations. Also, considering the growth factor of civil aviation, so far, India does not have a resident leasing finance industry. The objective of this paper is to analyze the impact due to the currency fluctuation, current strategies by which airlines take proactive measures against this fluctuation and the policy reforms and facilitation by Government, which can lead to sustainable business operations.

Introduction

Any organization as part of their business operation that involves any of international trade such as a commodity, payment of invoices is subjected to transaction cost risk. Transaction risk refers to the impact of exchange rate changes on the value of committed cash flows (cash flows that lie in the future, but the nominal value of which is known). The time frame for committed transactions (the time between contracting and payment) may be short, or it can, in some cases, reach several years.

An operating airline involved in international /domestic operations, such as Air India, Indigo, AirAsia, the need to translate cash flows into different currencies arise. The uncertainty of future exchange rates gives the risk of exchange rate risk as among other risks that arise due to the influence of external factors such as Jet fuel price, political environment regulation, global economic cycles, seasonality effects, natural disasters, and external shocks. The effect of the foreign exchange risk to an airline varies according to the

scope of operation, demographics, corporate strategy and risk management practice. Forex affects airlines in different ways; it affects consumer decisions (inbound/outbound) when making travel plans, influences airline supply decisions, which in turn impact airline finances, both day-to-day operating activities (profitability) and balance sheet valuations.

For airlines, the larger share of foreign currency exposure is often to the US dollar because major cost items, such as fuel, maintenance, and overhaul costs, aircraft purchase and lease payments are denominated in US dollar.

(Source: Finnair annual report, 2018)

Review of Literature

Aircraft leasing is the process by which aircraft operators (airline) increase the capacity and operate the aircraft without having the financial burden of buying the aircraft. Capacity can be added by the carrier in two ways, Purchase of aircraft (new or used aircraft) or Lease of aircraft (new or used). The model by which each carrier acquires the aircraft differs as per the airline operating model and cost structure. Some of the widely used models in leasing an airplane is a finance lease, operating lease (dry-lease or wet-lease), and sale-and-leaseback. As the scope of this paper is limited to operating lease (dry lease, wet lease, and damp) and its impact on sustainable operations, the other methods of acquisition are not considered.

The conditions by which the lease transaction structure differs is based on how typically the elements such as Aircraft, Crew, Maintenance, and Insurance (ACMI) components associated with the leased assets are arranged. Further, the method of acquisition (finance/operating lease) is usually decided by the top management and the impact of the lease on the operating profit of the airline is stronger for low-cost carriers than that of full-service carriers. The effectiveness of the decision regarding the fleet is the main success factor in fierce competition.

The profitability of air transportation has a close correlation with economic growth, favourable business environment, and trade. Studies suggest that foreign exchange risk as most critical of all the financial risk exposures. Exchange rate risk is also considered to be the most critical of all the financial risk exposures.

Previous study has been done on the exchange rate fluctuation, interest rate, commodity rate in the context of aviation turbine fuel, as fuel is considered as one of the major cost components in the airline cost. About 30% of airline cost (in addition to fuel) from aircraft lease rents, maintenance costs to ground handling and parking charges abroad are dollar-denominated. Throughout the literature, the studies have not focussed on maintenance cost and leasing cost due to currency volatility. Hence it is felt the necessity to explore the same in the context of operating lease and aircraft maintenance.

Lease Structure

The purchase and operation of aircraft and related assets by an airline, aircraft lessor, or other entity are financed using many different structures. Any lease structure shall be a combination of any one of the basic three structure concepts, a loan secured by a mortgage over the aircraft, a capital market transaction, and the ownership and lease of the asset.

There are two main benefits of leasing for airlines:

- They can operate aircraft without the financial burden of buying them, and
- It helps in temporary increasing the capacity when needed

An operating lease structure differs from that of finance lease and other methods of acquisition as mentioned earlier in this paper. A simple operating lease structure involves owners/lessors who lease the aircraft to the airlines, which in turn, will pay monthly lease rentals to owners/lessors. The amount of lease rentals depends on the make, model, age of the fleet, current market value, country of operation and also creditworthiness of the airline who leases the aircraft.

Growing Aircraft Leasing Market

As of Jan 2020, total commercial aircraft in India is 673 (www.knowindia.net) and expected to reach 1, 100 by 2027. The global market report by airbus, traffic forecast to double in the next 15 years. Demand for 39,210 passengers and freight aircraft over the next 20 years.

Airline Lease Rentals Payments

Lease payments are required to be made under the contract, usually fixed on monthly installments. The common payments include the following

1. Lease rent - the monthly payment (either fixed or variable) for a certain period.
2. Maintenance reserves - Lessee, in addition to rent, pay lessor’s contributions for future higher-level maintenance.

Lessors generally charge an airline between 0.85 % to 1.2 % (lease rate factors - LRFs) of the aircraft's list price / Current Market value (the cost of the aircraft) as rental per month. On the other hand, the lease rentals vary as per the age, lease duration, current market value of the equipment, which is again affected by the supply and demand of the type of the aircraft. An average lease monthly rentals range from 180,000 USD to 315,000 USD based on the age of the aircraft (typically on A320 series / Boeing 737).

Source: Aircraft Values of end-of-life A320/737 families to neo/MAX -
Leeham News and Analysis

Considering the average lease rentals and lease transactions it's estimated that annual lease rentals of around Rs 10,000 crores are being transferred to the leasing companies, which accounts for 15% of the total revenues. More than 70 % of the fleet are on operating lease with the lease terms six years to twelve years and denominated in USD. As the growth is expected to continue, the total transaction value will be triple by 2040.

Exchange Rate Risk

Exchange rate risk is the financial risk arising from fluctuations in the value of a base currency against foreign currency in which a company or individual has assets or obligations. The size of the FX risk varies, depending on the nature and scope of an airline's operations, as well as its corporate strategy.

Exchange rate movements affect expected future cash flow and therefore changing the home currency value of foreign revenues or costs. There is an inherent Exchange Risk in an international trade transaction denominated in a foreign currency, as an adverse movement in the exchange rate may reduce the realization of home currency for an exporter or increase the cost for an importer.

Studies have shown that from the period 2000 till 2010, Rupee to US dollar has been fluctuating between 1US \$ = Rs. 40-Rs. 50. Post-2013 Rupee has depreciated to over Rs. 60 to 1 USD. Further, a search on the internet (FXSTREET) reveals the current value (as in Dec 2019) of INR to USD is 71.73350 INR per 01 USD. From the trend line, it is also confirmed that INR currency is depreciating compared to USD in the past 09 years.

Source: exchangerates.org.uk/USD-INR-exchange-rate-history.html

Revenue Impact

Exchange rate fluctuations impact airline finances, both day-to-day operations, profitability, and balance sheet. Airlines in Asia are particularly exposed to foreign exchange risk and are at the mercy of the fluctuations in the value of the US dollar. The strength of the US dollar has put additional stress on emerging markets, including airlines in India, where the currencies have fallen by about 10-15%, plus oil has gone up by 10-15%.

The gradual depreciation of the rupee will lead to increased cost of leasing in rupee terms. Airlines may not be able to pass on the same to the passenger, squeezing their margins further, which is not sustainable in the long run.

Risk Management Strategy

An Airline can take the following strategies on managing risk related to forex on a fluctuation.

Cause	Effect
Do nothing approach	Accepting all risks by default
Hedging a portion of exposures	Protecting the portion (determining which exposures can and should be hedged).
Hedging all Possible exposure.	Eliminating risk as a whole

To reduce this exchange risk for a transaction to be concluded at a future date, Forward Contracts are being booked. It is a mechanism through which the rates are fixed in advance for purchase or sale of foreign currency needed at that future date. The financial hedge has been a popular strategy among airlines in managing fuel price. The commonly stated reason is that hedging stabilizes fuel prices, and therefore, overall costs, cash flows, and profits.

INR Denominated Leases

The possible solution or number of ways to reduce or eliminate FX volatility is through the modification of the contract as allowed by the accounting standards. The viable approaches would be to denominate the lease agreements in the functional currency of the lessee and shortening the period of the lease agreement. The earlier case requires acceptance by the lessor, and lessors usually prefer to denominate the lease in USD due to the advantage of USD. The latter will incur additional costs on leasing due to the negative relation between lease duration and lease rates. As the lease duration increase, the lease rate optimizes and vice versa.

Also, India is currently ranked a lowly 56th out of 72 countries on the World Aircraft Repossession Index (WARI), indicates the theoretical ability to repossess (legal environment for aircraft repossessions) the aircraft in a cost-effective and timely manner by the lessor. The measure is taken in seven factors (repossession, insolvency, deregistration, export, judgments and arbitral awards, preferential liens and political stability). India needs to make necessary reforms to take it among the top nations.

Also, India is currently ranked a lowly 56th out of 72 countries on the World Aircraft Repossession Index (WARI). By 2040, India will undertake significant reforms to take it among the top 10 nations.

Airlines in India have a combined fleet size of more than 600 planes and over 700 planes on order. A report by leasing firm reported that around 76 % of the aircraft flown in India are on operating lease, the highest in the world. A majority of the lessors operate out of Ireland due to its attractive tax norms. Around 80 percent of all maintenance work of airlines in value terms is carried out by units overseas and the government wants to boost the sector locally. The government will adopt suitable policy interventions to create a favourable ecosystem for the development of MRO in the country

Resident (India-Based) Leasing Industry

Another approach is to develop a structure that would establish an entity where the transaction happens with the same functional currency, in this case, INR or otherwise creation of resident aircraft leasing in the country. However, India does not have its leasing industry and a home-based lessor so far, and as such, all this amount is sent to lessors based out of India.

Though aircraft financing is the most profitable segment, there are no entities in the country exploring this line of business in India. It is also pertinent to note that India ranked 63rd in Doing Business 2020: World Bank Report.

Currently, Ireland is a top aviation leasing destination; the main reasons are due to a highly favourable tax regime, benefits of double taxation avoidance treaties, the absence of with-holding tax on lease rentals, low corporate tax, and special exemption on dividend with-holding tax on profit extraction. Recently, China has built its home-based leasing industry and attracted investment through specific low-tax dispensation. On the contrary, India imposes taxes such as stamp duty, import duty, GST, income, and capital gains taxes, among others. It is an opinion that the tax regime in India require rationalization.

Local regulators need to allow long-term financing entities like insurance companies, mutual funds, and pension funds to invest in securities of entities engaged in rupee-based leasing. Starting an NBFC or an investment trust in the GIFT City will require specific approvals from RBI. The “Rupee Raftaar” report contains a detailed list of proposals. Global Aircraft Leasing Market valued USD 44,879 billion in 2017 approximately and is anticipated to grow with a healthy growth rate of more than 4.78% over the forecast period 2018-2025. Global Aircraft Leasing Market to reach USD 68,321.4 billion by 2025.

A resident leasing industry in India will contribute to GDP, prevent the foreign exchange loss, reduce the leasing cost for airlines in India and create high-end jobs.

Hedge Accounting Solutions

Hedging is a risk management strategy/mechanism used to reduce or eliminate the fluctuations in costs, providing an airline with a more assured cost structure, thereby reducing an airline's risk to exposure.

A currency hedge is an instrument that allows a company to protect against unfavourable movements in exchange rates. Financial derivative instruments such as FX forwards, swaps, and options are widely used techniques for hedging. This approach requires the airline to enter into contracts with external parties.

Hedging practice includes natural hedges, cash flow hedges, and fair value hedge. Hedging is done to reduce the swings in profits. However, they will have a price that reflects the value of that counterbalance.

The company hedges its currency, interest rate, and jet fuel exposure using a variety of derivative instruments, such as forward contracts, swaps, and options, in compliance with the risk management policy approved annually by the Board of Directors.

Conclusion

Airlines can respond to, or mitigate, risks associated with FX fluctuations in various ways, including via financial hedging instruments. However, such a discussion is beyond the scope of this paper and that requires further study.

When cash outflows only are to be hedged, options hedging at 2% below par (i.e., using out-of-the-money currency call options) would yield the best results. The Hedging option should be considered based on the risk-tolerance of the concerned firm. The organization should analyze inflation rates and interest rates to make sure that the forward rates are properly priced.

Every hedge has a cost; so, before the organization decides to use hedging, the organization must evaluate, if the benefits received from it to justify the expense. The study is limited to forex fluctuation, risk management, and home-based leasing industry. Future studies can be conducted on the challenges for India in establishing the resident leasing industry and an ecosystem for leasing business in India.

Since the hedging market for USD/INR hedges is not liquid beyond the 12-month range, airlines tend to leave this exposure unhedged, and the depreciation of the Indian rupee creates pressure on the airline business model. The percentage of a company's foreign currency exposure hedged will often be directly related to the predictability of its foreign currency cash flows. The greater the degree of predictability, the greater the percentage of exposure that is hedged.

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